

Semantic Information Retrieval – Knowledge Hub

Report R2

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1 Summary

This deliverable is dedicated to describing the activity performed to set up a knowledge hub of heterogeneous multisource textual documents related to the project.

The knowledge hub (KH) is intended as a facility to aid users with different backgrounds, authorizations and need to find information they need in an easy way, by either formulating queries expressed in natural language to an information retrieval systems (IRS), and / or by navigating into a knowledge graph of “topics” and relationships among “topics”, in which documents have been automatically organized.

The techniques used to design and implement the KH and to classify the documents and the underlying IRS are based on the state-of-the-art “Large Language Models”.

An experiment of user-evaluation has been set up in which several models publicly available have been tested and evaluated on a representative subset of documents by applying distinct indexing techniques so as to identify the best performing model-representation.

This is a first step useful to identify the baseline we will select for the fine-tuning of the model.

2 Introduction

The Knowledge Hub activity phase was focused on the design of the architecture of the MAP (Knowledge Hub) multimedia document platform concerning the aspects relating to the collection of multimedia documents, both structured, semi-structured and unstructured texts, possibly containing images, maps, and tables, coming from different information sources distributed on the Web, in order to enable both searches by content and navigation from interested stakeholders. The results of the previous phases of the project were fundamental to carry out this activity, and specifically: characterization and definition of the different information sources and documents to be analysed and the definition of the use cases of the platform (Phase 0).

Based on such information we have been able to identify the information (IR) and knowledge retrieval (KR) models most suitable for creating the platform.

First, the documents have been harvested and locally stored.

Then, the methods of representation and indexing of their content have been selected. We decided to apply two different strategies:

1. the first one is a consolidated on-the-shelf solution, based on traditional discrete bag-of-words indexing techniques exploiting either the documents' metadata when available or the text extracted from the document content and the Geonode tool to guarantee access to all documents; in this case the user query is keyword-based and the documents are retrieved if they contain the query keywords in the respective metadata;
2. the second solution is more experimental and up-to-date, based on state-of-the-art semantic indexing methods using continuous bag of words. As far as the queries we decided to allow complete freedom to users so that they can formulate natural language queries or keywords' queries. In this case the documents are retrieved if their contents are semantically close to those of the query.

To allow the implementation of the first solution some minimal metadata have been associated to the documents and also the text of the document has been filtered and provided as a basis for the extraction of index terms by relying on Geonode facilities for managing texts.

As far as the second solution, the retrieval models we experimented to perform the retrieval task are several chosen among the Large Language Models available publicly. All these models imply the representation and management of the "semantics" of information in a document corpus which has been provided as training set; then, by means of empiric statistical inference that identifies "regularities" in such data, they learn how to predict missing words in a sentence, or how to continue a sentence, or to answer a query, and, finally, to retrieve relevant documents in an ad hoc retrieval task activated by a user query. Such "semantics" models are the most effective in the case one has heterogeneous collection of documents, with different genres, structures, topics, and one wants a natural language querying interaction, since they can retrieve documents which do not contain the specific query words, but synonymous terms or concepts related with the query concepts.

Specifically, this activity has been divided into 3 tasks:

Task 1.3.1 - In collaboration with ISPRA we have analyzed the sources and type of documentation to be included within the Knowledge Hub. This has brought to the definition and characterization of documents in relation to their format (e.g. pdf, xml, html, tiff, jpg, svg, gml, etc.), nature (e.g. texts, images, tables, graphs), genre (e.g. scientific articles, technical reports, news, data, georeferenced maps, satellite images, photographs, metadata)

Task 1.3.2 - Successively, we have identified the IR and KR models best suited for the documents selected. To this end, we have chosen pretrained large language models that have been set up for the ad hoc retrieval task and based on evolutions of BERT, Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers, which is the Google state-of-the-art model using a transformer architecture, a deep neural network, with self-attention mechanisms, that allows to keep the context of words into account when creating their representation as embeddings, i.e., as vectors of continuous numeric values in a latent semantic space.

Task 1.3.3 - Once the models have been selected, we defined the architecture of the Knowledge hub document platform by specifying the preprocessing phase that our corpus of documents should undergo to become a readable input to the selected models. The formats of the input documents, should be simple text with punctuation marks allowing the identification of single words, i.e., tokens; of sentences, ending with punctuation marks like full stop or semicolon, etc.; and of paragraphs, starting with a new line. So the non-conforming documents consisting in pdf files had to be “translated” into text.

Furthermore, the processing steps have been identified which has implied the selection of the implementation libraries and environment in order to code the whole process.

We experimented hybridized techniques, for example, the contents of queries and documents was represented by applying different embedding methods, and the same for the ranking of documents using different similarity measures.

Finally, we identified the most suitable open software for the implementation of the components, the indexing, the retrieval and the classification components of the Knowledge hub platform.

The following implementation requirements have been considered:

- first the simplicity of the implementation: we did not want to reinvent the wheel;

- the availability of up-to-date functions implementing state-of-the-art language models;
- Intuitiveness of use;

considering that there are a number of open source IR libraries after a review we selected `SentenceTransformer` python framework (<https://github.com/UKPLab/sentence-transformers>) that makes several Hugging face pretrained models available for sentence embeddings, and we exploited also the python library NLTK (Natural Language Toolkit - <https://www.nltk.org/>) for managing corpus documents and different tokenization strategies (i.e. the aforementioned subdivisions of documents in sentences, paragraphs, etc.).

As far as the classification of the document corpus into the topics, identified in the previous phase, (PHASE 0), functionality which is necessary to building the knowledge graph for documents navigation directed by topics, we first identified “definitions” of each topic keywords in renowned and authoritative open domain websites, in the form of textual abstracts. Topic keywords were accounted for in the UNESCO thesaurus <http://vocabularies.unesco.org/thesaurus>, an RDF SKOS concept scheme, but without definitions. We then enriched the pre-existing thesaurus by adding those definitions in the web of data. The result is available both as linked data (<http://rdfdata.get-it.it/inforac/>) and through a SPARQL endpoint (<http://fuseki1.get-it.it/inforac/sparql>). We then have set up an evaluation experiment by randomly selecting a subset of 50 documents of the collection, engaging 3 users who read these documents and formulated 10-30 queries each and for each query identified the list of their respective relevant documents among the 50 ones.

We evaluated some metrics of retrieval effectiveness. For our purposes we deemed meaningful to compute mean Average Precision (mAP) of different combinations of pretrained language models, documents representations based on different chunks definitions, and matching function (either dot product or cosine similarity for chunking and K-NN with fuzzy document cardinality for documents ranking score computation) to identify the best performing combination and applied this model setting to classify the whole collection into the topics, by considering the topics’ definitions as queries. This way a document can be assigned to multiple topics to a different extent.

At the end of activity, we have reached all expected results: the sources of information have been characterized, the most suitable information and knowledge

retrieval models have been identified, and we have motivated the technical choices made, explained the functionality of the Knowledge Hub, as well as the first prototypal implementation and evaluation tests have been carried out which are the basis for the tool to be implemented in the future. We have at the same time guaranteed an on the shelf consolidated solution based on more tradition IR techniques which can be implemented using the features of the Geonode tool.

3 phase 0: selection of the documents' corpus

1.1 Information sources

This step was aimed at identifying the sites and archives with potentially interesting documents and at carrying out their characterization with respect to some meaningful dimensions. The results are reported in Report 0 (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8082923](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8082923)) and a table has been deployed in a repository of the project to share all the information collected:

https://cnrsc.sharepoint.com/:x:/r/sites/UNEP-MAP/Documenti%20condivisi/General/UNEP-Map/Fase0/information_sources_F0-T01.xlsx?d=w970e672311ce4771b797a1685661bd2b&csf=1&web=1&e=1fplaY.

The documents in these information sources are more than 10000, mainly files, and most of them are in PDF format. Most information sources (20 out of 24) contain documents, and 3 of these resources also share images and tables, while only 3 out of 24 provide geographical layers. As far as the thematic or thematic resources are concerned, they are dedicated to 3 themes: law, regulation and management of the sea (13 out of 24), pollution (7) and biodiversity (2). Finally, 21 of the classified repositories are open to the public, while the remaining 3 are private or have restricted access.

From Regional Marine Pollution Emergency Response Centre for the Mediterranean Sea (REMPEC - <https://www.rempec.org>), Regional Activity Centre for Specially Protected Areas (SPA/RAC - <https://www.rac-spa.org>), Regional Activity Centre for Sustainable Consumption and Production (SCP/RAC - <http://www.cprac.org>), Priority Actions Programme/Regional Activity Centre (PAP/RAC - <https://paprac.org/>), UNEP-MAP library (<https://www.unep.org/unepmap/resources/publications?/resources>) and UNEP library where the author was marked as UNEP-MAP

(https://wedocs.unep.org/discover?filtertype=author&filter_relational_operator=equals&filter=UNEP%2FMAP), we harvested, through website scraping, all the documents. As meaningful metadata dimensions, for each documents downloaded, the following have been considered:

- Title of the document;
- Handle PID;
- Document URL;
- language ISO 639 1; documents are mainly in English but other languages are also represented like Italiana, French, etc.;
- Publication year;
- Image link;
- File extension (pdf, xml, etc.); most of the documents are in pdf;
- Keywords (when available);
- Abstract (when available).

1.2 Documents and metadata focused harvesting (used libraries and R code and Python code)

For document harvesting, some code has been developed both by CNR-IREA in the R language and from INFO-RAC in Python language.

The python code developed by INFO-RAC in this sense is available through the INFO/RAC GitHub KMP library scraping repository (<https://github.com/INFO-RAC/KMP-library-scraping>) under GNU GPL license.

To share the files produced for the harvesting process, a GitHub repository (https://github.com/IREA-CNR-MI/inforac_ground_truth) was created. The "scraping" folder contains the R and Python scripts developed for scraping, the output of these files are in the "results" folder. The complete list of downloaded documents was stored in the files `listOfDocuments_complete.csv` and `listOfDocuments_complete_II.csv`, the scripts `read_pdf.R` and `read_pdf_II.R` are related to the transformation and validation of the PDF files into text, the files `unepMapDocs_pdf` and `unepMapDocs_pdf_II` contain all the metadata for each downloaded document in CSV and R archive (RDS) format.

The harvesting process covered 6 sites (see previous paragraph) containing 15,161 documents of different types, formats and extensions (e.g. PDF, XSLX, JPG). Only those documents with a PDF extension were downloaded, i.e. 14,987 documents.

The conversion to TXT only affected those documents that were indicated as being in English on the respective pages and were accessible during the download. During the conversion process, we came across some PDF documents that were empty, with no readable text or only images. PDF files with these characteristics were therefore not converted. Of the initial total, only 7,280 were retained for further analysis.

1.3 Preprocessing phase

From a first analysis we could identify that the pdf documents are the majority of the total ones.

Among them a small subset consists of scanned documents, thus images, in pdf format: thus, their content should be extracted by using some OCR tool, and for these we have decided to rely on their metadata for their indexing.

For the remaining pdf documents, we selected those in English language (5246 documents corresponding to about one third of the total) and we used the R package *pdftools* (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/pdftools/index.html>) to filter and extract the text from the pdf files.

The R package *Tokenizers* makes available lexicographic functions to extract tokens directly from pdf files, to extract stems of words, and n-grams. This was used in a first experimental phase to analyze the presence of meaningful words in the selected documents.

Finally, functions written in python language have been used for tokenization since the implementation environment that was selected has many libraries in python (hugging face).

4 phase 1: Indexing of selected corpus and IR based on NL queries

For the indexing and retrieval of the identified textual corpus of documents we have decided to apply in parallel two different strategies:

- A conservative and well consolidated solution based on “on the shelves” implementation that could be immediately applied by Geosolution implementing the platform of the project;

- A state-of-the-art strategy that needs experimental and testing research activity on large language models, that we wanted to experience to provide an alternative more effective solution.

4.1 Retrieval solution based on GeoNode and PostgreSQL

The conservative and well-consolidated strategy that uses available solutions already tested and integrated with the rest of the project platform is based on the use of GeoNode. GeoNode is an open-source platform for sharing geospatial data and creating interactive maps. It is built on top of the Django web framework and uses various components to manage and serve geospatial data. However, GeoNode itself doesn't provide functionality for indexing textual documents. Indexing and searching textual documents are handled by other tools integrated with GeoNode. We have decided to make use of PostgreSQL's full-text indexing and search capabilities to integrate indexing of documents' metadata with GeoNode. PostgreSQL has a robust set of features for full-text search, and GeoNode, can leverage these capabilities. In order to do this, it is necessary to enable the full-text search in PostgreSQL. This implies to set the GeoNode's data models to include a field for the textual content to index, which in our case is the documents titles (plus keywords and abstract when available). A trigger can be set in PostgreSQL to automatically update the full-text search index as new data are inserted or updated in the corresponding GeoNode table. Finally, GeoNode queries can be modified to include full-text search capabilities by using the @@ operator to perform full-text searches against the textual field.

4.2 Retrieval solution based on application of large language models

Although there are open source tools for the "on the shelves" implementation of a full-text information retrieval systems of textual documents, such as Elasticsearch or Anserini, capable of indexing the whole content of the documents and enabling searches using natural language queries, the technologies they use for NLP are traditional, based on discrete bag of words, which have demonstrated to be less effective than the novel NLP techniques evolved in recent years. Current document indexing methods are based on the representation of document content by

continuous bag of words, i.e., vectors of real values defined in a dense multidimensional continuous space, called embedding space, which is implemented through neural mechanisms. These methods, instead of applying logic to perform reasoning on a knowledge base of rules elicited from expert linguists, like previous methods do, they apply empirical inference to identify “regularities” in data so as to be able to predict missing words, or the continuation of a sentence, the answer to a question in conversations, or the retrieval of relevant documents in an ad hoc retrieval task.

The most recent neural architecture is called transformer, which allows the network to learn the semantics of documents chunks, i.e., words, sentences, paragraphs or even n-grams by taking into account the context in which they are placed within the text. In fact, synonyms, words with similar meaning and documents’ chunk similar contents are represented by nearby vectors in the embedding space. The transformer architecture is much efficient and effective than previous sequence neural models, such as recurrent neural networks and Long Term - Short Term memory networks, which were much demanding in terms of training data and computational time.

These approaches have increased the retrieval effectiveness of traditional systems by 30%. BERT, created by the Google research group, is the prototype architecture of transformers which then evolved into various variants of which ChatGPT is also an example. An embedding model, i.e. a set of dense vectors corresponding to chunks of documents, is created through a network training phase starting from a large corpus of documents. This phase requires a lot of computational resources and especially big data for the corpus, which is generally of the order of billions of documents corresponding to several terabytes. For this reason, when implementing an IR system based on embedding, already existing embedding models are used, i.e. pretrained models, which are available in the most used NLP libraries such as hugging face. There are many, most of them for the English language but also for multiple languages such as <https://huggingface.co/bert-base-multilingual-uncased>.

4.1.1 Transformer neural architecture for Large language Models generation

The transformer architecture is a neural network architecture introduced by Vaswani et al. in 2017, that has drastically changed NLP and the analysis of data sequences, such as time series, image series and the like.

Transformers are highly scalable and have demonstrated remarkable performance on large-scale datasets, making them suitable for various applications.

They consist of an encoder and a decoder, both composed of multiple identical hidden layers. The encoder processes input sequences while the decoder generates output sequences. The encoder and decoder share the same set of parameters, promoting parameter efficiency and simplifying the model architecture.

Moreover, the Transformer includes a component named self-attention mechanism, which is its core innovation, allowing the model to weigh input sequences of text differently thus capturing long dependencies efficiently.

Self-attention is extended with multi-head attention, enabling the model to focus on different aspects of the input simultaneously, enhancing its capacity to learn complex patterns. As transformers don't inherently understand the order of inputs, positional encoding is added to the input to provide information about the position of tokens in a sequence. Each attention layer is followed by a feedforward neural network, facilitating the model's ability to capture non-linear relationships in the data. Transformers use layer normalization and residual connections to stabilize training and ease the flow of gradients through the network.

4.1.2 Pretrained Large Language Models

Large language models refer to advanced NLP models that are built on deep learning architectures, specifically leveraging neural networks with a vast number of parameters. These models are characterized by their ability to understand, generate, and manipulate human-like language patterns. One of the key innovations in this domain has been the development of transformer-based architectures, such as OpenAI's GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer) series and BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers). They have enormous scales, often comprising tens or hundreds of billions of parameters. The vast number of parameters enables these models to capture intricate language nuances and learn from massive amounts of diverse text data. They are typically pre-trained on big datasets, allowing them to learn general language patterns and context. The pre-

training phase involves predicting missing or masked words in sentences, helping the model understand the contextual relationships between words.

After pre-training on a big dataset, the models can be applied to represent in the same semantic latent space a novel collection of documents and to perform a required task for which it was pre-trained. They can also be fine-tuned by a transfer learning approach for other specific tasks, such as text classification, summarization, translation, question answering and ad hoc retrieval. This transfer learning paradigm enhances their ability to perform well on a wide range of NLP tasks. So, while pre-training provides a strong foundation, these models are often fine-tuned on task-specific datasets to adapt their knowledge to particular applications and improve performance.

For the implementation of our experimental information retrieval solution we decided to code the prototypal software in python by using the hugging face library, that offers a large collection of pre-trained models tuned for various tasks.

We decided to focus on sentence-transformers. SentenceTransformers allows to generate text and image embeddings by computing sentence embeddings for more than 100 languages. These embeddings can then be compared for example with dot product or cosine-similarity to find sentences, for example in a query, with a similar meaning. This can be useful for semantic search.

For sentence / text embeddings, a variable length input text is mapped into a fixed sized dense vector. A high level sketch of the basic network architecture is depicted below:

We feed the input sentence or text into a transformer network like BERT. BERT produces contextualized word embeddings for all input tokens in our text. As we want a fixed-sized vector representation (vector u), we need a pooling layer. Different pooling options are available, the most basic one is mean-pooling, which simply averages all contextualized word embeddings BERT has generated. This

process gives us a 768 fixed sized dimensional output vector independently of how long was the input sentence.

Once the sentence embeddings have been generated, they can be compared by computing a similarity measure as in the following sketched diagram:

Within this framework we have selected the following pre-trained Large Language Models based on sentence-transformer architectures:

- <https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/msmarco-distilbert-cos-v5>: it maps sentences & paragraphs to a 768-dimensional dense vector space and was designed for semantic search. It has been trained on 500k (query, answer) pairs from the MS MARCO Passages dataset(Microsoft Machine Reading Comprehension) which is a large scale dataset focused on machine reading comprehension, question answering, and passage ranking. DistilBERT is a distilled version of the BERT model. It retains much of the pre-training power of BERT while using a smaller number of parameters, making it computationally more efficient and suitable for deployment in resource-constrained environments.
- <https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L6-v2>: it maps sentences & paragraphs to a 384 dimensional dense vector space and can be used for tasks like clustering or semantic search.
- <https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/msmarco-roberta-base-ance-firstp>: this is a port of the ANCE FirstP Model, which uses a training mechanism to select more realistic negative training instances to the sentence-transformers model: it maps sentences & paragraphs to a 768 dimensional dense vector space and can be used for tasks like clustering or semantic search.
- <https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/msmarco-bert-base-dot-v5>: it maps sentences & paragraphs to a 768-dimensional dense vector space and was designed

for semantic search. It has been trained on 500K (query, answer) pairs from the [MS MARCO dataset](#).

- <https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/msmarco-distilbert-base-tas-b>: it is a port of the [DistilBert TAS-B Model](#) to sentence-transformers model: It maps sentences & paragraphs to a 768 dimensional dense vector space and is optimized for the task of semantic search.

4.1.3 Schema of the indexing mechanism exploiting a pretrained Large Language Model

The high level diagram of the indexing module that we have implemented uses embeddings of either sentences or fixed windows size n-grams, or paragraphs extracted from the text of the selected collection of PDF documents and is illustrated below.

Indexing Process using sentence embeddings

For its implementation we used the hugging face library and the pretrained models listed above. This indexng phase is performed off-line, only once, or every time the document collection is updated.

An improvement of the process to better adapt it to the semantics of the document collection involves a model fine-tuning phase, which involves updating an existing pre-trained model, with the embeddings of the documents from the collection that is to be used. This involves training with the new collection. This step is omitted in the illustrated indexing scheme.

From left to right: first the pdf collection is parsed and the text of each document is extracted by filtering out non-meaningful tokens. Then chunks of text of each document are provided to a selected large language model by suiting their dimension to the constraints required by the input of the model. In the implementations we provided three distinct definitions of the chunks: sentences, fixed windows size or n-grams, and paragraphs. For each chunk, an embedding vector of given dimension specific for each model is generated. Notice that in the hugging face environment this latter operation is transparently done by the functions of the library without the need for the programmer to bother about these aspects. Finally, the embeddings are stored in a database.

This indexing process was performed on a subset of 50 documents randomly extracted from the collection since we wanted to identify the best performing setting defined by the choice of combinations of the triple: model, chunk representation, similarity measure.

4.1.4 Schema of the retrieval mechanism exploiting a pretrained Large Language Model

To perform ad hoc retrieval using Hugging Face's Transformers library, we followed these steps:

Document Embedding;

Query Embedding; similarly, using the same pre-trained models we embedded the user's query into the same latent semantics embedding space.

Overall Scoring: Calculation of a relevance score between the query embeddings and each document embeddings. Common methods include cosine similarity, dot product, or other similarity metrics.

Rank Documents: Rank the documents by their relevance scores in descending order to present the most relevant documents to the user.

While ad hoc retrieval itself is not a specific task integrated into Hugging Face's library, the library provides pre-trained transformer models that can be used for the crucial steps involved in building an ad hoc retrieval system, such as document and query embedding.

Although we had to implement the scoring and ranking steps ourselves.

So, while ad hoc retrieval is not a predefined task, Hugging Face's Transformers library can be a valuable resource for building components of an ad hoc retrieval system within your NLP project.

In more details, after the embedding vectors have been created by the indexing mechanism and stored into a database it was possible to activate the retrieval module (see Figure 2), which, taking a user query, compares it by calculating a distance (or similarity) between each embedding vector in the database corresponding to a chunk of a document and the embedding vectors of the query, also created using the same language model used during document indexing.

This comparison was defined in different ways to test the best solution depending on the model and document chunk representation, specifically:

- We used either a dot product or a cosine similarity between single pairs of embedding vectors representing a document chunks and a query chunk, to compute an overall score for each document with respect to the query we combined the similarity scores of each document by applying a min-max aggregation: this way we guarantee that all query chunks are as similar to any document chunk to the scores computed by the matching, accounting by the max aggregation the fact that a document can have subparts very relevant to the query while other parts may be not relevant at all;
- We applied a simplified approach to compute the overall document score with respect to the query by first averaging the embeddings of all query chunks to obtain a virtual representative query embedding vector and then computed, as

previously, either a dot product or a cosine similarity between single pairs of embeddings representing a document chunk and the query virtual embedding vector. We then aggregated the results of the similarity scores for each document in two different ways:

- Avg_0 : either by taking the maximum of the scores for each document as overall document score, thus accounting for the most relevant subpart of each document;
- Avg_1: or by defining the overall document score by summing up the i scores of each document considering $i=2, \dots$, total number of chunks of each documents. This way, we account for the best i -th matching chunk of each document.

As a result of the query evaluation we can return the K documents ranked in decreasing order of their overall score computed in one the ways described above. Generally, it is useful to offer the user a graphical user interface both for formulating queries and for exploring the documents resulting from the searches carried out.

In our case, since our aim was to test the different models with the different settings of both the inputs and of different similarity metrics, we implemented everything in hugging phase environment.

Nevertheless, based on our prototypal implementation when designing the user interface one has all data needed to show the original retrieved documents together with the snippet, i.e., the text of the sentences that allowed their retrieval, so that the user can evaluate whether the document is really what he was looking for.

4.1.5 Pseudo-code in python using hugging face library to index a collection of textual documents and to perform ad hoc retrieval given any NL query

Just to exemplify the simplified code to create a simple ad hoc retrieval system using the Hugging Face Transformers library in Python, we will use a pre-trained language model such as BERT to index and retrieve documents.

The script uses the BERT model to encode both the documents and the query and calculates cosine similarity to retrieve the top matching documents.

Remember that this is a basic example, and one can further enhance the retrieval system by fine-tuning the model, adding more complex scoring methods as we did,

or using more advanced techniques depending on specific use case and requirements.

First, we make sure to have the necessary libraries installed:

```
bash
pip install transformers
pip install sentence-transformers
```

Then let's create a Python script to set up the retrieval system:

```
python
import os
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd

from sentence_transformers import SentenceTransformer, util

from transformers import BertTokenizer

# Set the variable to your documents directory path where you stored the
textual documents to index

documents_dir = r'C:\path\to\your\documents\directory'

# Load a pre-trained BERT model for encoding text
model_name = 'bert-base-uncased'
model = SentenceTransformer(model_name)

# Load a pre-trained tokenizer for text preprocessing
tokenizer = BertTokenizer.from_pretrained(model_name)

# Directory where your documents are stored (each document in a separate
file)
# documents_dir = 'your_documents_directory'

# Create an index of document embeddings
document_embeddings = []

# Create a list of document IDs (e.g., filenames) for retrieval
document_ids = []

for filename in os.listdir(documents_dir):
    with open(os.path.join(documents_dir, filename), 'r', encoding='utf-8')
as file:
        text = file.read()
        embeddings = model.encode(text, convert_to_tensor=True)
        document_embeddings.append(embeddings)
        document_ids.append(filename)

# Convert document embeddings to a NumPy array
document_embeddings = np.vstack(document_embeddings)

# Function to perform ad hoc retrieval
```

```

def retrieve_documents(query, top_k=5):
    query_embedding = model.encode(query, convert_to_tensor=True)
    scores = util.pytorch_cos_sim(query_embedding, document_embeddings)[0]
    top_indices = np.argsort(scores)[-top_k:][::-1]
    top_documents = [(document_ids[i], scores[i]) for i in top_indices]
    return top_documents

# Example queries and retrieval
queries = ["environmental impact of deforestation", "renewable energy
sources"]
for query in queries:
    top_results = retrieve_documents(query)
    print(f"Query: {query}")
    for doc_id, score in top_results:
        print(f"Document: {doc_id}, Score: {score:.4f}")
        with open(os.path.join(documents_dir, doc_id), 'r', encoding='utf-
8') as file:
            print(file.read()) # Print the content of the retrieved
document
        print("\n")

```

One can also set the path in cmd

```
set documents_dir = "C:\path\to\your\documents\directory"
```

4.1.6 Future refinements: BERT multilingual model and fine tuning

In the implementation we considered only models for the English language, nevertheless in hugging face there are BERT-based models specifically trained for multiple languages.

These models are part of the multilingual BERT family. One can use these models for various natural language processing tasks in multiple languages.

One of the popular multilingual BERT models is called "bert-base-multilingual-uncased." see <https://huggingface.co/bert-base-multilingual-uncased>

It covers a wide range of languages, including Italian.

One can use the Hugging Face Transformers library to load and utilize these models in your Python code. Here's an example of how to load the multilingual BERT model for Italian:

```

python
from transformers import BertTokenizer, BertModel

# Load the multilingual BERT tokenizer and model
tokenizer = BertTokenizer.from_pretrained("bert-base-multilingual-uncased")
model = BertModel.from_pretrained("bert-base-multilingual-uncased")

# Example text in Italian
italian_text = "Questo è un esempio di testo in italiano."

```

```

# Tokenize and encode the Italian text
inputs = tokenizer(italian_text, return_tensors="pt", padding=True,
truncation=True)

# Pass the input through the model to get embeddings or perform tasks like
classification, translation, etc.
outputs = model(**inputs)

# Access embeddings or other model outputs as needed
embeddings = outputs.last_hidden_state

```

Make sure you have the Hugging Face Transformers library installed (`pip install transformers`) to use the code above.

To fine tune an already trained model for ad-hoc retrieval by adding textual documents and their titles as queries requires a significant amount of computational resources. Here's a simplified example of how one might approach this using Hugging Face Transformers. This is a basic illustration, and the actual fine-tuning process for a retrieval model may require domain-specific data and expertise. The first phase is data preparation: one needs a dataset that includes textual documents and their queries, which can be the corresponding documents titles. Each data point should consist of a document, a title, and a relevance label (indicating whether the document is relevant to the query). The second step is data preprocessing to tokenize and encode both the document and the query. One can use the same BERT tokenizer mentioned earlier. Finally, one has to define a retrieval model architecture that takes a query and a document as input and outputs an overall relevance score. One can fine-tune a pre-trained BERT model for this task.

Here's a simplified example of how one might define the model:

```

python
import torch
from transformers import BertModel, BertTokenizer
import torch.nn as nn
class DocumentRetrievalModel(nn.Module):
    def __init__(self, model_name):
        super(DocumentRetrievalModel, self).__init__()
        self.bert = BertModel.from_pretrained(model_name)
        self.cosine_sim = nn.CosineSimilarity(dim=1, eps=1e-6)

    def forward(self, query_input_ids, document_input_ids):
        query_outputs = self.bert(query_input_ids)
        document_outputs = self.bert(document_input_ids)

```

```
        similarity_scores = self.cosine_sim(query_outputs[0],
document_outputs[0])
    return similarity_scores
```

Training: Use a dataset to train the retrieval model. One needs to define a suitable loss function, and optimize the model's weights using gradient descent. **Inference:** After training, one can use the fine-tuned model to perform ad hoc retrieval. Here's an example of how one might do this:

```
python
def retrieve_documents(query, documents, model, tokenizer, top_k=5):
    query_input = tokenizer(query, return_tensors="pt", padding=True,
truncation=True)
    query_input_ids = query_input["input_ids"]

    document_inputs = tokenizer(documents, return_tensors="pt",
padding=True, truncation=True)
    document_input_ids = document_inputs["input_ids"]

    similarity_scores = model(query_input_ids, document_input_ids)
    top_indices = torch.argsort(similarity_scores, descending=True)[:top_k]
    top_documents = [documents[i] for i in top_indices]
    return top_documents

# Example queries and retrieval
queries = ["environmental impact of deforestation", "renewable energy
sources"]
documents = ["Document 1 text goes here.", "Document 2 text goes here.",
...] # Replace with your documents
model = DocumentRetrievalModel("bert-base-uncased")

for query in queries:
    top_results = retrieve_documents(query, documents, model, tokenizer)
    print(f"Query: {query}")
    for doc in top_results:
        print(f"Document: {doc}")
    print("\n")
```

Depending on specific use case, you may also need to consider additional techniques such as negative sampling and evaluation metrics like Mean Average Precision (mAP) to assess the model's performance.

5 phase 2: Effectiveness evaluation of state-of-the-art IR models

5.2.1 Building the ground truth for benchmark

To test the various implementations, we have selected a representative subset of 50 English pdf documents belonging to the collection, from now on named benchmark collection. This was done by randomly selecting a subset of documents representative of all scraped sources; these documents are indeed heterogeneous as far as their genre, length, topic domain and thus representative of all types.

5.2.2 Evaluation metrics: mAP

The metric we computed is mean Average Precision.

Mean Average Precision (mAP) is a performance metric commonly used to evaluate the accuracy of information retrieval systems. It is widely employed in the field of information retrieval.

Its definition is based on the computation of the retrieval precision which is a measure of how many of the retrieved documents are relevant to the query at hand. It is calculated as the ratio of true positives (documents correctly identified as relevant) to the sum of true positives and false positives (documents incorrectly identified as relevant):

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}} \quad |$$

In the case of information retrieval, the terms are defined as follows:

- True Positives (TP): The number of relevant documents that were correctly retrieved by the system.
- False Positives (FP): The number of non-relevant documents that were incorrectly identified as relevant by the system.

The recall measure, also known as sensitivity or true positive rate, is another metric used together with precision to measure how the system can retrieve all relevant documents in the collection. Recall is the ratio of true positives (documents correctly identified as relevant) to the sum of true positives and false negatives (documents that were not identified as relevant but are actually relevant). Its definition is the following:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}} \quad |$$

The Average Precision (AP) is a way to summarize the precision-recall curve for a model across different levels of confidence or thresholds on the rank of retrieved

report the mAP averaged over all users and all queries by considering different matching definitions.

Several column names represent the parameters passed to the computing function. "Ch_per_doc_<number>" is the parameter controlling the number of the best chunks considered for computing the document relevance value. When <number>=None, it means that all chunks are taken into account. The second (Boolean) parameter "avg_<0|1>" controls if the relevance is an average of similarity scores (avg_1) , or if it corresponds to their sum (avg_0). More in detail:

- Ch_per_doc_N_Avg_0 indicates that the sum of similarity scores of the considered number N of best document chunks was computed(N); For instance, N=1 means that only the chunk with highest score is used, that is, similarity of the document to the query is defined as the maximum similarity computed across the document chunks. For N=2, the first two best "performing" chunks are considered. Etc.
- Ch_per_doc_N_Avg_1 indicates that the average of the the best N similarity scores of the document chunks is computed;
- Ch_per_doc_None indicates that all chunks of the documents are considered.
- In this table the similarity is defined as the cosine similarity.

The column named "rank_doc_embeddings" reports the mAP values when the query is represented by a single virtual averaged embedding vector (see references 4, 5, 6 on averaging embeddings).

The last column named "max" reports the best mAP for the given setting in the row.

It can be easily noticed that three distinct models produce the maximum mAP = 0.64 for different settings by using *cosine similarity* between pairs of embedding vectors. Nevertheless, the most stable model under different input settings (both window and paragraph) and different matching definitions is all-MiniLM-L6-v2.

The second table, here below, reports the mAP values when changing the similarity metric by using the *dot product*.

In this case the best performing model is msmarco-distilbert-base-tas-b that, When feeded with chunk defined by sentences, it reaches a mAP = 0.65 when taking into account from 4 to 6 best matching document chunks using both the sum or their average scores.

We thus select this last model with the setting chunks=sentences, number of chunks per document to consider in the matching from 4 to 6 and either sum of scores or their average..

	chunk type	window size	pretrained large language model used	ch_per_d																				ch_per_doc		max	
				oc_1_avg	oc_1_avg	oc_2_avg	oc_2_avg	oc_3_avg	oc_3_avg	oc_4_avg	oc_4_avg	oc_5_avg	oc_5_avg	oc_6_avg	oc_6_avg	oc_7_avg	oc_7_avg	oc_8_avg	oc_8_avg	oc_9_avg	oc_9_avg	oc_10_avg	oc_10_avg	None_avg	None_avg		
0	sentence	384	msmarco-distilbert-cos-v5	0,60	0,60	0,61	0,61	0,64	0,64	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,36	0,48	0,64
1	window	384	msmarco-distilbert-cos-v5	0,60	0,60	0,61	0,61	0,60	0,61	0,59	0,59	0,57	0,59	0,56	0,58	0,55	0,57	0,55	0,58	0,54	0,57	0,54	0,57	0,38	0,47	0,61	
2	paragraph	384	msmarco-distilbert-cos-v5	0,61	0,61	0,62	0,61	0,62	0,62	0,61	0,61	0,61	0,61	0,61	0,61	0,60	0,60	0,61	0,61	0,60	0,60	0,60	0,60	0,60	0,36	0,47	0,62
3	sentence	256	all-MiniLM-L6-v2	0,61	0,61	0,61	0,61	0,62	0,62	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,35	0,53	0,63	
4	window	256	all-MiniLM-L6-v2	0,61	0,61	0,64	0,64	0,62	0,63	0,61	0,62	0,60	0,61	0,59	0,60	0,59	0,60	0,58	0,61	0,58	0,61	0,58	0,62	0,37	0,51	0,64	
5	paragraph	256	all-MiniLM-L6-v2	0,62	0,62	0,64	0,64	0,63	0,63	0,64	0,64	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,35	0,52	0,64	
6	sentence	512	msmarco-roberta-base-ance-f	0,57	0,57	0,59	0,59	0,61	0,61	0,60	0,60	0,59	0,59	0,59	0,59	0,59	0,59	0,59	0,59	0,59	0,59	0,59	0,59	0,28	0,44	0,61	
7	window	512	msmarco-roberta-base-ance-f	0,60	0,60	0,59	0,60	0,57	0,58	0,55	0,57	0,53	0,57	0,53	0,57	0,51	0,55	0,51	0,54	0,50	0,54	0,49	0,53	0,28	0,49	0,60	
8	paragraph	512	msmarco-roberta-base-ance-f	0,60	0,60	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,61	0,61	0,60	0,60	0,60	0,60	0,60	0,59	0,59	0,58	0,58	0,58	0,58	0,58	0,26	0,42	0,62	
9	sentence	512	msmarco-bert-base-dot-v5	0,63	0,63	0,64	0,64	0,64	0,64	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,28	0,47	0,64		
10	window	512	msmarco-bert-base-dot-v5	0,61	0,61	0,62	0,63	0,60	0,60	0,58	0,58	0,58	0,60	0,57	0,59	0,54	0,57	0,54	0,57	0,52	0,55	0,51	0,55	0,28	0,48	0,63	
11	paragraph	512	msmarco-bert-base-dot-v5	0,64	0,64	0,64	0,64	0,64	0,64	0,64	0,64	0,64	0,64	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,61	0,61	0,60	0,26	0,46	0,64		
12	sentence	512	msmarco-distilbert-base-tas-t	0,61	0,61	0,63	0,63	0,64	0,64	0,65	0,65	0,65	0,65	0,65	0,65	0,64	0,64	0,64	0,64	0,64	0,64	0,64	0,28	0,49	0,63		
13	window	512	msmarco-distilbert-base-tas-t	0,63	0,63	0,61	0,62	0,60	0,61	0,58	0,61	0,56	0,59	0,55	0,59	0,55	0,59	0,54	0,59	0,53	0,58	0,53	0,58	0,29	0,53	0,63	
14	paragraph	512	msmarco-distilbert-base-tas-t	0,61	0,61	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,64	0,64	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,63	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,62	0,26	0,50	0,64		

6 phase 3: Categorizing the document corpus into topics

6.3.1 Building topic embeddings

For the creation of topic embeddings we first defined the topics that were identified by keywords. To this end we mined authoritative sources such as the United Nation Climate Change web site, FAO, EU commission documentation and other websites to collect for each of them an abstract.

In the following we report the topics keywords and the correspondent textual descriptions. Corresponding Linked Data access URI are reported in parenthesis.

Climate change (<http://rdfdata.get-it.it/inforac/concept10360>)

According to United Nations Climate change refers to long-term shifts in temperatures and weather patterns. Such shifts can be natural, due to changes in the sun’s activity or large volcanic eruptions. But since the 1800s, human activities have been the main driver of climate change, primarily due to the burning of fossil fuels like coal, oil and gas.

Burning fossil fuels generates greenhouse gas emissions that act like a blanket wrapped around the Earth, trapping the sun’s heat and raising temperatures.

The main greenhouse gases that are causing climate change include carbon dioxide and methane. These come from using gasoline for driving a car or coal for heating a building, for example. Clearing land and cutting down forests can also release carbon dioxide. Agriculture, oil and gas operations are major sources of methane

emissions. Energy, industry, transport, buildings, agriculture and land use are among the main sectors causing greenhouse gases.

Marine biodiversity (<http://rdfdata.get-it.it/inforac/marine-biodiversity>)

United Nations define Marine biodiversity as the variety of life in the ocean and seas. The ocean is one of the main repositories of the world's biodiversity. It constitutes over 90 per cent of the habitable space on the planet and contains some 250,000 known species, with many more remaining to be discovered—at least two thirds of the world's marine species are still unidentified.¹

The ocean, and the life therein, are critical to the healthy functioning of the planet, supplying half of the oxygen we breathe² and absorbing annually about 26 per cent of the anthropogenic carbon dioxide emitted into the atmosphere.³

Evidence continues to emerge demonstrating the essential role of marine biodiversity in underpinning a healthy planet and social well-being. The fishery and aquaculture sectors are a source of income for hundreds of millions of people, especially in low-income families, and contribute directly and indirectly to their food security. Marine ecosystems provide innumerable services for coastal communities around the world. For example, mangrove ecosystems are an important source of food for more than 210 million people⁴ but they also deliver a range of other services, such as livelihoods, clean water, forest products, and protection against erosion and extreme weather events.

Thus marine biodiversity is a critical aspect of all three pillars of sustainable development—economic, social and environmental—supporting the healthy functioning of the planet and providing services that underpin the health, well-being and prosperity of humanity.

Sustainability and blue economy (<http://rdfdata.get-it.it/inforac/concept7775>)

It is now a widely used term around the world with three related but distinct meanings- the overall contribution of the oceans to economies, the need to address the environmental and ecological sustainability of the oceans, and the ocean economy as a growth opportunity for both developed and developing countries.

United nations define sustainability and blue economy that comprises a range of economic sectors and related policies that together determine whether the use of ocean resources is sustainable. An important challenge of the blue economy is to understand and better manage the many aspects of oceanic sustainability, ranging from sustainable fisheries to ecosystem health to preventing pollution. Secondly, the blue economy challenges us to realize that the sustainable management of ocean resources will require collaboration across borders and sectors through a variety of partnerships, and on a scale that has not been previously achieved.

It is also intended as sustainable use of ocean resources for economic growth, improved livelihoods, and jobs while preserving the health of ocean ecosystem.

blue economy also includes economic benefits that may not be marketed, such as carbon storage, coastal protection, cultural values and biodiversity.

Pollution (<http://rdfdata.get-it.it/inforac/concept6445>)

National Geographics defines pollution as the introduction of harmful materials into the environment. These harmful materials are called pollutants.

Pollutants can be natural, such as volcanic ash. They can also be created by human activity, such as trash or runoff produced by factories. Pollutants damage the quality of air, water, and land.

Many things that are useful to people produce pollution. Cars spew pollutants from their exhaust pipes. Burning coal to create electricity pollutes the air. Industries and homes generate garbage and sewage that can pollute the land and water. Pesticides—chemical poisons used to kill weeds and insects—seep into waterways and harm wildlife.

All living things—from one-celled microbes to blue whales—depend on Earth's supply of air and water. When these resources are polluted, all forms of life are threatened.

Pollution is a global problem. Although urban areas are usually more polluted than the countryside, pollution can spread to remote places where no people live. For example, pesticides and other chemicals have been found in the Antarctic ice sheet. In the middle of the northern Pacific Ocean, a huge collection of microscopic plastic particles forms what is known as the Great Pacific Garbage Patch.

Air and water currents carry pollution. Ocean currents and migrating fish carry marine pollutants far and wide. Winds can pick up radioactive material accidentally released from a nuclear reactor and scatter it around the world. Smoke from a factory in one country drifts into another country.

Marine spatial planning (<http://rdfdata.get-it.it/inforac/concept17119>)

EU commission defines Maritime spatial planning (MSP) as the tool to manage the use of our seas and oceans coherently and to ensure that human activities take place in an efficient, safe and sustainable way.

Objectives of Maritime spatial planning are the following:

- *reducing conflicts and creating synergies between different activities*
- *encouraging investment through predictability, transparency and legal certainty*
- *increasing cross-border cooperation between EU countries to develop renewable energy, allocate shipping lanes, lay pipelines and submarine cables etc*
- *protecting the environment by assigning protected areas, calculating impacts on ecosystems and identifying opportunities for multiple uses of space*

Fishery and aquaculture (<http://rdfdata.get-it.it/inforac/concept601>)

FAO (1988) introduced a definition of aquaculture which reduces its confusion with capture fisheries:

Aquaculture is the farming of aquatic organisms, including fish, molluscs, crustaceans and aquatic plants. Farming implies some form of intervention in the rearing process to enhance production, such as regular stocking, feeding, protection from predators, etc. Farming also implies individual or corporate ownership of the stock being cultivated. For statistical purposes, aquatic organisms which are harvested by an individual or corporate body which has owned them throughout their rearing period contribute to aquaculture, while aquatic organisms which are exploitable by the public as a common property resources, with or without appropriate licences, are the harvest of fisheries.

The above definition is significant as it introduces a social criterion (ownership of the stock throughout the rearing period) to qualify the production technology aspects. Although the FAO definition of aquaculture is an important contribution to our understanding of aquaculture, grey areas remain especially in relation to ricefields and culture-based fisheries. FAO classifies rice-cum-fish culture as aquaculture but there are complex inter-relationships between wild fish and aquaculture in ricefields which defy generalisation and definition. Farmers have caught wild fish in ricefields since time immemorial, often building trap ponds to harvest them when water levels fall at the end of the rainy season. The fish benefit from the modified rice field which, besides providing them with a habitat, also facilitates harvest. Farmers may also make the rice field dikes and screen outlets higher to facilitate growth and harvest of wild fish without resorting to either feeding or intentionally stocking wild or hatchery-raised seed.

Stocking of water bodies with either wild or hatchery-raised seed is aquaculture if the stock is owned individually or by a corporate body until harvest but it becomes capture fisheries if there is open access for the general public. Complex social issues relating to use of traditionally communal water bodies for aquaculture lead to difficulties, often at the expense of the rural poor.

Governance (<http://rdfdata.get-it.it/inforac/concept10360>)

There is no universally accepted definition of Governance when used in political literature. We owe the concept to Plato who was the first to use the Greek word κυβερνάω, meaning to steer a ship, metaphorically, in the context of steering Men. Over the years, the word has been used generically and the concept has evolved to encompass relationships between stakeholders in a variety of set ups. In the present highly dynamic environment, politically, socially, economically, and culturally, the term means different things in different contexts and the use of an adjective with the word governance has become almost mandatory for it to make any sense at all.

The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), in its 1997 policy paper, defined governance as “the exercise of economic, political and administrative authority to manage a country’s affairs at all levels. It comprises the mechanisms, processes and institutions through which citizens and groups articulate their interests, exercise their legal rights, meet their obligations and mediate their differences”. This definition was endorsed by the Secretary-General’s inter-agency sub-task force to promote integrated responses to United Nations conferences and

summits. Over the past 10 years, the number of country level programmes on governance supported by the United Nations system has expanded considerably.

Each topic description was represented by using the best performing model identified in the evaluation tests to produce their embeddings. Either an average virtual embedding vector or N different embedding vectors were derived so as to be able to apply the matching model most suited for the documents' classification.

6.3.2 Classifying documents to build a knowledge graph

To build the documents knowledge graph, which is functional to provide user with a guide to navigate in the collection of documents, it is necessary to classify documents with respect to the topics. To this end, the topics representations, i.e., their embeddings, are used as query embeddings and their matching with the documents chunks embeddings are computed. Then the documents can be ranked in decreasing order of satisfaction to the query topic descriptions.

Thus, a document belongs to all topics with distinct degrees and each node of the knowledge graph can be defined to contain the list of documents in decreasing order of overall relevance score to a topic description.

The graphic user interface can show just the first K most relevant documents when clicking a node identifying a topic, with K determined based on statistical analysis of the relevance scores. Alternatively, K can even be specified by the user.

On the other side, when clicking an edge of the graph connecting two nodes it means that the user wants to retrieve documents that are relevant to both the respective topics of the nodes.

To build this ranked list an intersection has to be applied so that the documents will be listed in decreasing order of their minimum relevance score in the two node lists, thus ensuring that the (fuzzy) intersection of the lists is performed.

A second possibility is to associate with a topic only documents with relevance score (the similarity score) greater than a threshold value, i.e., a cut-off level for the ranked list. This way the truncated ranked lists retrieved for each topic will contain a

possibly different subset of the document collection and a different number of documents. Nevertheless, the truncated ranked lists retrieved for two different topics can still overlap one another.

We performed the computation of relevance (similarity) scores in different ways, by basing the computation on the best model identified in the aforementioned benchmark.

Topics/themes are represented by long descriptions. They are then split into several chunks (sentences) and similarities of those chunks with corpus document chunks have been computed. The result, for each topic, is a matrix of as many rows as the topic chunks and as many columns as the documents (document chunk scores are aggregated following the methodologies described in the previous section 5.2.3). From this matrix three are the ways to aggregate the document-topic scores to generate an overall score for each pair topic-document:

- The first method, referred to as “min max” is to choose the minimum score of each column (i.e. the minimum similarity across topic chunks, where similarity of the chunk is the max similarity across document chunks). By this aggregation we guarantee that the overall relevance score of a pair topic-document is the most pessimistic evaluation of the similarity between the topic and the document reflecting the similarity of all the topic chunks with any document chunk;
- The second approach, called “max-max”, consists in the choice of the maximum score per each column, so that the overall score reflects the best matching between any topic chunk and any document chunk. By applying this method, the overall relevance score reflects the best matching between any single topic chunk and document chunk. This choice allows to better separate topic attribution to documents.
- The third way to compute the overall scores, named “average topic”, is finally applied by first averaging the embeddings of all the topic chunks in the same way discussed above, and then by simply computing the (cosine) similarity of this representative embedding with the document embeddings.

The following figure represents the distribution of the overall relevance scores across methodologies and topics. It can be observed that the distributions for the max-max aggregation are on average more “Gaussian shaped” than those of the other aggregations , being unimodal for most of the topics.

Considering the semantics of the overall relevance score computed with the max-max aggregation and the distributions of the scores we have chosen this as the best aggregation method.

Document score frequencies for each topic

To investigate the correlation of the overall scores computed with the max-max method, we report in the following figure the overall relevance scores of documents retrieved for pairs of topics. This allows to grasp the behavior of topic dependencies as reflected by the relevance scores of documents for pairs of topics. Each scatterplot presents a couple of topics (axes). Documents are positioned in the space of the two topics, according to their overall relevance (similarity) scores. It can be seen that while for high overall scores (top right quadrants) the distributions are spread reflecting the fact that we have documents that may deal with only one of the topics or with both of them, when the overall scores are both very small (bottom left quadrant) the distributions are more correlated reflecting the fact that these documents are irrelevant to both topics considered. Generally, we can observe that there are no documents highly relevant for one topic and not relevant for the other (top left and bottom right quadrants), meaning that there is always a correlation

between pairs of topics.

7 Conclusions

The present deliverable reports the work done to design and to experiment with state-of-the-art methods for full text information retrieval of the textual documents of the project.

We indicated both a straightforward solution based on Geonode and postgresQL implementation and an experimental solution based on pretrained Large Language models.

The last solution is up to date and has been tested with distinct settings on 5 different large language models so as to identify the best one to be used for documents classification into the topics of the project.

The results of this experimental solution will be useful to organize the documents into the topics of the project to design a knowledge graph that can aid the user navigation into the collection.

8 Bibliography

1. Gerard Salton and Chris Buckley (1991) Global Text Matching for Information Retrieval, *Science* Vol. 253, No. 5023 (Aug. 30, 1991), pp. 1012-1015
2. Ponte, J. and Croft, W. (1998). A language modeling approach to information retrieval. In *Proceedings of the 21st ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval*, pages 275–281.
3. Ashish Vaswani, Noam Shazeer, Niki Parmar, Jakob Uszkoreit, Llion Jones, Aidan N. Gomez, Lukasz Kaiser, Illia Polosukhin (2017) Attention is all you need, in *proc. Of the 31st Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NIPS 2017)*, Long Beach, CA, USA.

4. Sanjeev Arora, Yuanzhi Li, Yingyu Liang, Tengyu Ma, Andrej Risteski; A Latent Variable Model Approach to PMI-based Word Embeddings. Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics 2016; 4 385–399. doi: https://doi.org/10.1162/tacl_a_00106
5. Arora, Sanjeev, Yingyu Liang and Tengyu Ma. (2017) A Simple but Tough-to-Beat Baseline for Sentence Embeddings. Proc. of the International Conference on Learning Representations (2017).
6. Ben Coleman, 2020. Why is it Okay to Average Embeddings?. url: <https://randorithms.com/2020/11/17/Adding-Embeddings.html>
7. Reimers, Nils and Iryna Gurevych. "Sentence-BERT: Sentence Embeddings using Siamese BERT-Networks." Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (2019).
8. Reimers, Nils and Iryna Gurevych. "Making Monolingual Sentence Embeddings Multilingual Using Knowledge Distillation." ArXiv abs/2004.09813 (2020): n. pag.

9 Repository of ground truth benchmark

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